

MINIMALLY INVASIVE INTERVENTION OF MALLORY - WEISS SYNDROME

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Abstract. The incidence of Mallory-Weiss syndrome has increased almost 2-2.5 times in recent decades, which is due not only to the improvement of endoscopic diagnostic methods, but also to the increase in alcohol consumption by the population. The purpose of the study. To study the effectiveness of endoscopic hemostasis methods, in particular electrocoagulation in Mallory-Weiss syndrome. Materials and methods. The study included 43 patients who were hospitalized in the Khorezm branch of the Republican Scientific and Practical Center for Emergency Medical Care for Mallory-Weiss syndrome, in the period from 2015 to 2020. Results. For the treatment of these patients, we used the endoscopic method of electrocoagulation. Of all the patients, 41 (95%) were male, and only 2 (5%) belonged to the female sex. Conclusion. In our study, it was repeatedly proved that age-related changes are the main factors that contribute to the rupture of the mucous layer, the older a person is, the more easily the gastric mucosa is damaged.

Keywords: Mallory–Weiss syndrome; bleeding; endohemostasis; relapse.

Relevance. The incidence of Mallory-Weiss syndrome has increased almost 2-2.5 times in recent decades, which is due not only to the improvement of endoscopic diagnostic methods, but also to the increase in alcohol consumption by the population. The number of bleeding recurrences in Mallory-Weiss syndrome reaches 6-42%, postoperative mortality is 10-17%, and the total mortality is 11.8-4.8%. The disease mainly occurs in representatives of the stronger sex at the age of 45-60 years, who consume excessive amounts of alcohol [1].

With Mallory-Weiss syndrome, it is possible to achieve the cessation of stagnant bleeding with the endoscopic method of hemostasis. If there is a relapse, then the use of the combined method of endoscopic hemostasis gave a good result. Endoscopic infiltration methods of stopping bleeding in patients with Mallory–Weiss syndrome are the most effective, and few recurrent methods of treatment [2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. Endoscopic technologies for Mallory-Weiss syndrome during operational search activities, the detainee was detained [7]. In Mellori-Weiss syndrome, endoscopic treatments allow the use of adequate

surgical tactics, determining the degree of tearing of the floors, the intensity of bleeding [8].

The purpose of the study. To study the effectiveness of endoscopic hemostasis methods, in particular electrocoagulation in Mallory-Weiss syndrome.

Materials and methods. The study included 43 patients who were hospitalized in the Khorezm branch of the Republican Scientific and Practical Center for Emergency Medical Care for Mallory-Weiss syndrome, in the period from 2015 to 2020.

Results. For the treatment of these patients, we used the endoscopic method of electrocoagulation. Of all the patients, 41 (95%) were male, and only 2 (5%) belonged to the female sex.

The average age of men was 55-56 years, and the average age of women was 67-68 years.

Endoscopic measures were performed within 3 hours after hospitalization. All patients were hospitalized in the intensive care unit to prepare the upper digestive tract for endoscopic manipulations.

Electro-endoscopic hemostasis is mainly used. Electro-endoscopic hemostasis was effectively used in 40 (93%) patients, only 3 (7%) patients with stage IV Mallory-Weiss syndrome underwent the traditional method of treatment in the form of surgery. In all other cases, the electrocoagulation method of hemostasis was completely effective, without repeated bleeding, regardless of the stage of Mallory-Weiss syndrome. Also had no side effects of the application.

Conclusions. In our study, it was repeatedly proved that age-related changes are the main factors that contribute to the rupture of the mucous layer, the older a person is, the more easily the gastric mucosa is damaged. Endoscopic method of homeostasis electrocoagulation can achieve stable hemostasis in Mallory-Weiss syndrome, and reduce the number of repeated bleeding. It is also more relevant since most patients had above the first stage.

References:

1. Тимербулатов Ш.В., Сагитов Р.Б., Ямалов Р.Б. Хирургическая тактика при синдроме Мэллори-Вейса. Вестник Национального медико-хирургического Центра им. Н.И. Пирогова. – 2010. – Т 5, №1. – С. 39-43.
2. Якубов, Ф. Р., Сапаев, Д. Ш., Эрниязов, Э. А., Матқурбонов, Н. О., & Якубов, Р. Ф. (2023). Меллори-Вейсс синдромини кам инвазив усулларини қўллаган ҳолда ташхислаш ва даволаш. Биология ва тиббиёт муаммолари, 1(142), 143-145.

3. Рузибаев Р.Ю., Умаров Д.А., Сапаев Д.Ш., Рузметов Б.А. Результаты хирургического лечения хронического геморроя у больных с медикаментозной гипокоагуляцией. Проблемы биологии и медицины. 2022, №5 (139). – С. 185-191.
4. Якубов Ф.Р., Сапаев Д.Ш., Эрниязов Э.А., Маткурбонов Н.О. (2023). Современный подход в лечение при синдроме Меллори - Вейсса. Международная конференция академических наук, 2(1), 103–105. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7563829>
5. Якубов Ф.Р., Эрниязов Э.А., Сапаев Д.Ш., Маткурбанов Н.О. (2023). Улучшения лечебно-диагностического процесса при синдроме Меллори – Вейсса. Academic research in modern science, 2(2), 154–156. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7559998>
6. Yakubov F.R., Erniyazov E.A., Sapaev D.S. (2023). Modern Treatment of Mallory-Weiss Syndrome. International journal of health systems and medical sciences, 2(4), 27–33. Retrieved from <https://inter-publishing.com/index.php/IJHSMS/article/view/1415>
7. Якубов Ф.Р., Сапаев Д.Ш., Эрниязов Э.А., Маткурбонов Н.О., Якубов Р.Ф. Меллори - Вейсс синдромини кам инвазив усулларини қўллаган ҳолда ташхислаш ва даволаш. Биология ва тиббиёт муаммолари. 2023, №1 (142). – Б. 143-145.
8. Якубов Ф.Р., Сапаев Д.Ш., Эрниязов Э.А., Маткурбонов Н.О. (2023). СОВРЕМЕННОЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ СИНДРОМА МЕЛЛОРИ - ВЕЙССА. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM, 2(6), 41–43. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7931860>

